

Appendix

1 Initial and final states

The following tables sum up the final rate state corresponding to each initial rate state, for each possible case. Note that the states where both events have a starred occurrence rate are forbidden.

No event on the branch

In this particular case, the final state is always the same as the initial state.

One occurrence of E_i only on the branch

E_1		E_2	
Initial state	Final state	Initial state	Final state
(a_1, a_2)	(b_1, b_2)	(a_1, a_2)	(b_1, b_2)
(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)
(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2)
(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)
(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2)
(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)
(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)
(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)
(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2)
(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)
(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2)
(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)
(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)

Both events are present on the branch

$E_1 \rightarrow E_2$			$E_2 \rightarrow E_1$		
Initial state	Intermediate state	Final state	Initial state	Intermediate state	Final state
(a_1, a_2)	(b_1, b_2)	(c_1, c_2)	(a_1, a_2)	(b_1, b_2)	(c_1, c_2)
(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2)
(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)
(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)
(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)
(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2)
(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)
(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2)
(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(ν_1, μ_2^*)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)
(ν_1, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)
(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, ν_2^*)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(ν_1, ν_2^*)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2^*)
(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)	(μ_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2)
(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(μ_1, ν_2)	(μ_1^*, μ_2)	(ν_1^*, ν_2)	(ν_1, μ_2)	(μ_1, μ_2)

2 Likelihood function for a single branch

Let \mathcal{T} be a tree, and \mathcal{B} a branch of this tree, of length l . We consider two events E_i , $i \in \{1, 2\}$, of respective occurrence rates $(\mu_i, \mu_i^*, \nu_i, \nu_i^*)$. Each event is assumed to occur at most once on \mathcal{B} .

We detail here the likelihood function for this single branch, the three possible cases being treated separately. Let $f_{\mathcal{B}}$ be the likelihood for the branch \mathcal{B} , given the parameter values.

No event on the branch

Let a_1 (resp. a_2) be the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) on the branch.

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} = e^{-l(a_1+a_2)}$$

One occurrence of E_i , $i \in \{1, 2\}$ on the branch

In this case, we define:

- a_1 (resp. a_2) as the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) before the occurrence of E_i on the branch
- b_1 (resp. b_2) as the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) after the occurrence of E_i on the branch.

Those parameters take different values depending on the initial states on the branch, and according to the model. We easily get

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\mathcal{B}} &= \int_0^l a_i e^{-a_1 t} e^{-a_2 t} e^{-b_1(l-t)} e^{-b_2(l-t)} dt \\ &= -\frac{a_i}{a_1+a_2-b_1-b_2} (e^{-l(a_1+a_2)} - e^{-l(b_1+b_2)}) \end{aligned}$$

When $(a_1 + a_2 - b_1 - b_2) \rightarrow 0$:

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} \rightarrow a_i l e^{-l(b_1+b_2)}$$

One occurrence of each event on the branch

In this subsection, we assume that the occurrence of E_i precedes the occurrence of E_j on branch \mathcal{B} ($\{i, j\} \in \{1, 2\}, i \neq j$).

By analogy with the previous case, we define:

- a_1 (resp. a_2) as the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) before the occurrence of E_i on the branch
- b_1 (resp. b_2) as the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) after the occurrence of E_i and before the occurrence of E_j on the branch.
- c_1 (resp. c_2) as the occurrence rate for E_1 (resp. E_2) after the occurrence of E_j on the branch.

Those parameters take different values depending on the initial states on the branch, and according to the model. We easily get

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\mathcal{B}} &= \int_0^l a_i e^{-a_1 t} e^{-a_2 t} \left(\int_0^{l-t} b_j e^{-b_1 x} e^{-b_2 x} e^{-c_1(l-t-x)} e^{-c_2(l-t-x)} dx \right) dt \\ &= \frac{a_i b_j}{c_1+c_2-b_1-b_2} \left(\frac{e^{-l(a_1+a_2)} - e^{-l(b_1+b_2)}}{b_1+b_2-a_1-a_2} - \frac{e^{-l(a_1+a_2)} - e^{-l(c_1+c_2)}}{c_1+c_2-a_1-a_2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

If all three denominators tend to 0,

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}a_i b_j l^2 e^{-l(b_1+b_2)}$$

When $c_1 + c_2 - b_1 - b_2 \rightarrow 0$,

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} \rightarrow \frac{a_i b_j}{b_1+b_2-a_1-a_2} \left(\frac{e^{-l(a_1+a_2)} - e^{-l(b_1+b_2)}}{b_1+b_2-a_1-a_2} - l e^{-l(b_1+b_2)} \right)$$

When $b_1 + b_2 - a_1 - a_2 \rightarrow 0$,

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} \rightarrow \frac{a_i b_j}{c_1+c_2-b_1-b_2} \left(l e^{-l(b_1+b_2)} - \frac{e^{-l(b_1+b_2)} - e^{-l(c_1+c_2)}}{c_1+c_2-b_1-b_2} \right)$$

When $a_1 + a_2 - c_1 - c_2 \rightarrow 0$,

$$f_{\mathcal{B}} \rightarrow \frac{a_i b_j}{c_1+c_2-b_1-b_2} \left(\frac{e^{-l(b_1+b_2)} - e^{-l(c_1+c_2)}}{c_1+c_2-b_1-b_2} - l e^{-l(c_1+c_2)} \right)$$